

Kinetics and Mechanism of Ag^+ Catalysed Oxidation of Alcohols by Peroxodisulphate Ion in Aqueous Medium

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The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of 3-butane-2-ol, 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol, *n*-butyl alcohol and allyl alcohol by peroxodisulphate ion in aqueous medium revealed that although these reactions are first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, first order in Ag^+ and zero order in substrate in any particular kinetic run, the pseudo first order rate constant is dependent on the concentration of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and substrate taken. The stoichiometry in case of 3-butane-2-ol is 1 : 1 and varies in case of 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol. Allyl acetate inhibits the rate appreciably indicating that the reaction involves free radicals or radical ions. The salt effect is negative and of primary exponential type. The product of oxidation in each case is the corresponding aldehyde. On the basis of kinetic behaviour reported and the products characterised, a general radical mechanism for these reactions has been proposed and the corresponding rate law has been derived.

OXIDATION of alcohols by peroxodisulphate ion is an interesting reaction. Although a large amount of work has been done to decide the mechanism of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of alcohols by peroxodisulphate ion, it is still undecided and differing kinetic behaviours have been reported. Thus Edwards *et al.*¹, found a 1.5 and 0.5 order in CH_3OH and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, while Stehlik and Fiala² observed half order inhibition by alcohol for these reactions. On the other hand, Khulbe and Srivastava³ reported zero order in alcohol and first order in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ for the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of 2-propanol. A detailed kinetic study of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of 3-butane-2-ol and 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol has been undertaken in order to arrive at a general mechanism for these oxidation reactions. The effect of temperature on the oxidation of *n*-butyl alcohol and allyl alcohol has also been carried out to test the isokinetic relationship. The results of these studies are presented and discussed in this paper.

Experimental

Methods and Materials :

3-Butane-2-ol (E. Merck), 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol (L. R. Aldrich) and allyl alcohol ; *n*-butyl alcohol (B.D.H. AnalaR) were used after distillation. Purity of the compounds was also checked by their boiling point. All the inorganic chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

The reaction was carried out in aqueous medium and its progress was followed by estimating the

unreacted $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ iodometrically by the method of Szabo, Gsyani and Galiba^{1,8}, as modified by Khulbe and Srivastava^{1,9}.

The IR spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-20, Infrared Spectrophotometer using KBr disc.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic behaviour :

Kinetic studies at constant ionic strength and at different concentrations of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and substrates show that the reaction in each case is first order in oxidant and zero order in substrate. However, the first order specific rate is dependent on the concentration of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ and the alcohol (Table 1). The specific rate is linearly related to Ag^+ (Table 2). In both the cases, the reaction exhibits negative salt effect of the exponential type (Table 3). The reaction shows appreciable inhibition of rate by allyl acetate (Table 4). The thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of the four alcohols under study are reported in Table 5. A plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger for different alcohols is linear, indicating the applicability of isokinetic relationship and the value of β calculated therefrom is 321.2°K.

The mole ratio of substrate to oxidant comes out to be 1 : 1 in case of 3-butane-2-ol while it varies in case of 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol.

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TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS ON THE SPECIFIC REACTION RATE

[AgNO₃]=1.0×10⁻³M μ=0.631M; Temp.=308K

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈]×10 ³ M	[Substrate]×10 ³ M	Specific rate sec ⁻¹ ×10 ⁵
3-butane-2-ol		
1.0	1.0	0.19
2.0	1.0	0.23
3.0	1.0	0.25
4.0	1.0	0.26
1.0	2.0	0.31
1.0	3.0	0.31
1.0	4.0	0.33
1.0	5.0	0.34
2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol		
1.0	1.0	0.040
2.0	1.0	0.053
3.0	1.0	0.060
4.0	1.0	0.067
1.0	2.0	0.057
1.0	3.0	0.070
1.0	4.0	0.070

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [AgNO₃] ON SPECIFIC REACTION RATE

Temp.=308K

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈]=0.01M [3-butane-2-ol]	or	[K ₂ SO ₄]=0.2M [2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol]=0.01M	AgNO ₃ ×10 ³ M	k×10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹ 3-butane-2-ol	k×10 ⁶ sec ⁻¹ 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol
1.0			1.0	0.19	0.38
2.0			2.0	0.38	0.70
2.5			2.5	0.47	0.83
3.0			3.0	0.55	1.00
3.5			3.5	0.65	—

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON SPECIFIC RATE

Temp.=308K

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈]=0.01M [3-butane-2-ol]	or	[AgNO ₃]=0.001M [2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol]=0.01M	Ionic strength μ	k×10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹ 3-butane-2-ol	k×10 ⁶ sec ⁻¹ 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol
0.031			0.031	6.2	1.0
0.061			0.061	5.3	0.93
0.091			0.091	4.6	0.85
0.121			0.121	4.0	0.78
0.151			0.151	3.7	0.75
0.181			0.181	3.4	0.71

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ALLYL ACETATE ON THE SPECIFIC REACTION RATE

Temp.=308K

[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈]=0.01M [3-butane-2-ol]	or	[AgNO ₃]=0.001M [2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol]=0.01M	[Allyl acetate]	k×10 ⁵ sec ⁻¹ 3-butane-2-ol	k×10 ⁶ sec ⁻¹ 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol
0.000			0.000	6.30	1.03
0.002			0.002	5.80	0.770
0.010			0.010	4.30	0.770
0.100			0.100	0.800	0.050

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Substrate	Temp. coeff.	Ea. K. cal mole ⁻¹	A×sec ⁻¹	ΔG [‡] K. cal mole ⁻¹	-ΔS [‡] E.U.	ΔH [‡] K. cal mole ⁻¹
3-butane-2-ol	1.08	12.7	1.99×10 ⁴	24.9	41.0	12.0
2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol	2.07	14.6	9.30×10 ⁴	26.0	37.9	14.0
n-butyl alcohol	2.25	16.3	9.43×10 ⁶	24.8	28.7	15.7
Allyl alcohol	2.40	17.9	4.15×10 ⁷	25.2	25.8	16.9

Analysis of the Product :

The product of reaction in case of 3-butane-2-ol and 2-methyl-3-butane-2-ol was isolated from the reaction mixture by distillation under reduced pressure. The distillate in each case gave +ve test for aldehydic group with Schiff's reagent. To characterise the different aldehydes formed, the 2,4-DNP derivatives of the products were prepared and recrystallised with alcohol, and checked for purity by TLC, and these were characterised by elemental analysis, m.p. IR and by co-tlc to be 3-butane-2-one and methyl-vinyl-ketone respectively.

Mechanism :

Taking into consideration the previous proposed mechanism for this redox system and on the basis of the kinetic results obtained and the products of oxidation characterised, the following general mechanism is proposed for the oxidation of these alcohols by S₂O₈²⁻ :

Applying steady state treatment to the different reactive intermediates viz. Ag²⁺, SO₄⁻ and RĊHOH, the following rate law is obtained for the consumption of peroxodisulphate ion with time :

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d}{dt} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] &= k_2 K [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \\
 &+ \left(\frac{K k_2 k_3 k_5}{k_6} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{ROH}]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{Ag}^+]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \dots \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $k_6 \gg K$ or k_2 or k_3 or k_5 , the second term of equation (1) will be very very small, which is kinetically indistinguishable and hence can be neglected. Thus the rate of peroxodisulphate consumption can be approximated to

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [S_2O_8^{2-}] = k_2 K [Ag^+] [S_2O_8^{2-}]$$

However, the possibility of utilisation of SO_4^+ , formed in the process (ii), in oxidising Ag^+ in preference to RCH_2OH according to the following reaction cannot be ruled out

If process (iii) occurs in place of process (ii), the rate law for the disappearance of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ works out to be

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [S_2O_8^{2-}] = \left[k_2 K + \left(\frac{k_2 K k_3 k_4}{k_5} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} [Ag^+] [S_2O_8^{2-}] \dots (2)$$

Thus, both the rate laws derived satisfy all the kinetic features observed in the oxidation of alcohols studied. However, the dependence of the rate on the concentration of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ can be attributed to the effect of trace impurities present⁴ even in the recrystallised samples of $K_2S_2O_8$.

Justification for the proposed mechanism :

Formation of $Ag S_2O_8^-$ complex in the first step by a reversible process is in accordance with the view of Bekier and Kijowski⁵, and Beilerian and Chaltykyan⁶. Large negative value of entropy of activation suggests that the first reversible step is a fast one while the second stage, the dissociation of $Ag S_2O_8^-$ into three ions is a slow process. The existence of Ag^{2+} and SO_4^+ in such redox systems has already been reported earlier by a number of workers⁷⁻¹⁰. SO_4^+ has been shown to abstract hydrogen from the substrate in preference to $\dot{O}H$ as also suggested earlier by Anbar and Neta¹¹ and Hayon and Simic¹². Greater tendency of direct oxidation by SO_4^+ by one electron transfer compared to that by $\dot{O}H$ has already been shown by a number of workers⁸⁻¹⁰ and recently has been confirmed by Steenken *et al.*¹³. Our assumption that Ag^{2+} and SO_4^+ are the chief reactive species is in agreement with the observation of Subbaraman and Santappa¹⁴, and of Higginson and Marshall¹⁵. The absence of participation of $\dot{O}H$ in such a redox system has already been confirmed by Kumar¹⁶, in his study of

oxidation of diols by peroxodisulphate ion. In the fifth and sixth steps $R\dot{C}HOH$ has been used for further reaction instead of $RCH_2\dot{O}$, the formation of which is justified by the observation of Gilbert *et al.*¹⁷ in their ESR studies wherein they have found that $Pr\dot{O}$ undergoes a fast unimolecular isomerisation into $Et\dot{C}HOH$ (k value of the order of 10^7 sec^{-1}).

Further, free radical nature of the reaction has also been confirmed by us by the observance of appreciable inhibitory effect on the reaction by allyl acetate.

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